

Synthesis of 4-(5-keto-2-phenyloxazolin-4-ylmethylene)-3-phenylisoxazol-5-one

V. K. Rao

Division of Plant Physiology & Biochemistry, Indian Institute of Horticultural Research, Hessaraghatta, Bangalore-560 089, India

E-mail : vkr5@yahoo.com

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Abstract : 3-Phenylisoxazol-5-one (1) reacts with hippuric acid and ethyl orthoformate in acetic anhydride to give 4-(5-keto-2-phenyloxazolin-4-ylmethylene)-3-phenylisoxazol-5-one (4) in a single step.

Keywords : 3-Phenylisoxazole-5-one, synthesis.

Reaction of nitrile oxides with 3,4-substituted 5-isoxazolones yielded 2,3,3-trisubstituted derivatives¹. Owing to my continued interest in isoxazoles fused to other heterocycles, I have attempted to synthesize fused pyrano[6,5-*d*]isoxazole (3) by heating 3-phenylisoxazol-5-one (1), hippuric acid (2) and triethyl orthoformate in Ac₂O. The absence of amide absorption in IR spectrum of the resulting red coloured product led me to believe that it was not the expected product 3. Based on the spectral data, the product was identified as 4-(5-keto-2-phenyloxazolin-4-ylmethylene)-3-phenylisoxazol-5-one (4, Scheme 1). 5-Isoxazolones, with at least one free hydrogen at 4th position, are known to exhibit tautomerism². The form 4a seems to represent the solid state with the absence of N-H absorption in the IR spectrum, whereas, ¹H NMR spectrum (in DMSO-*d*₆) showed a broad N-H peak at δ 4.45-4.60, and a singlet for methine proton at δ 6.94 due to predominance of form 4b in solution. Predominance of 4b is favored by polar solvents due to H-bonding. Even, 3-phenyl-5(4*H*)-isoxazolone exhibited N-H proton in the ¹H NMR spectrum when recorded in DMSO-*d*₆³.

The structure of 4 was confirmed by its synthesis through condensing 4-formyl-3-phenylisoxazol-5-one (5)⁴, with 2 in Ac₂O. Compound 4 was hydrolyzed with dil. KOH to form β-(3-phenyl-5-oxo-4-isoxazolyl)-α-benzamidoacrylic acid (6). ¹H NMR spectrum of compound 6 also showed the presence of N-H proton when recorded in DMSO-*d*₆ due to stability of tautomer 6b. Heating the amide (6) in Ac₂O resulted in its re-conversion to 4.

Scheme 1

The possible mechanism includes initial formation of 4-ethoxymethylene-2-phenyloxazol-5-one (7) and its subsequent condensation with 1 to yield 4 (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2

Experimental

M.ps. were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. UV spectra were recorded on Beckman-DU-64 spectrophotometer. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Bomem-100 FT-IR spectrophotometer. ^1H and ^{13}C NMR (DMSO- d_6) were recorded on Varian (200 MHz) and Varian (400 MHz) instruments, respectively, using TMS as internal standard. Purity of the compounds was monitored by TLC.

4-(5-Keto-2-phenyloxazolin-4-ylmethylene)-3-phenylisoxazol-5-one (4) :

(a) A mixture of 1 (1.61 g), 2 (1.79 g) and triethyl orthoformate (1.66 ml) taken in Ac_2O (5 ml) was heated in an oil-bath for 30 min. The resulting red solid (4) was washed with water, alcohol and dried (2.02 g, 61%), m.p. 192–193°, λ_{max} 486, 437 (sh) nm; ν_{max} 1798 (C=O), 1671 cm^{-1} (C=O); δ_{H} 4.45–4.60 (1H, br, N-H), 6.96 (1H, s, methine proton), 7.35–7.58 (10H, m, ArH); δ_{C}

100.62, 124.54, 127.36, 127.76, 129.19, 129.32, 130.94, 131.64, 133.34, 158.15, 163.32, 169.60; m/z (EI) 332 (M^+), 288, 260, 199, 155, 105.

(b) A mixture of 5 (1.89 g) and 2 (2.79 g) taken in Ac_2O (6 ml) was heated in an oil bath for 25 min. The separated compound 4 (2.15 g, 65%) was washed with water, alcohol and dried.

β -(3-Phenyl-5-oxo-4-isoxazolyl)- α -benzamidoacrylic acid (6) : A mixture of 1 N NaOH solution (10 ml) and 4 (3 g) was heated on a water-bath for 15 min and then neutralized with excess of 2 N HCl. The resulting yellow solid was washed with water and crystallized from aq. methanol (2.65 g, 84%), m.p. 175°; ν_{max} 3520, 3400, 1710, 1680, 1650 cm^{-1} ; δ_{H} 5.21–5.84 (1H, br, N-H), 6.05 (1H, s, methine proton), 7.40–7.94 (10H, m, ArH), 10.95 (1H, br, s, COOH); m/z (EI) 306 ($\text{M}^+ - \text{CO}_2$), 201, 161, 121, 105, 103.

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